

Comment on “Symmetries and turbulence modeling”

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The study by Klingenberg, Oberlack & Pluemacher [“Symmetries and turbulence modeling”, Phys. Fluids **32**, 025108 (2020)] proposes a new strategy for modeling turbulence in general. A proof-of-concept is presented therein for the particular flow configuration of a spatially evolving turbulent planar jet flow, coming to the conclusion that their model can generate scaling laws which go beyond the classical ones. Our comment, however, shows that this is not the case. Hence, their argument of having established a new and more advanced turbulence model cannot be confirmed. The problem is already rooted in the modeling strategy itself, in that a nonphysical statistical scaling symmetry gets implemented. Breaking this symmetry will restore the internal consistency and will turn all self-similar solutions back to the classical ones. To note is that their model also includes a second nonphysical symmetry. One of the authors already acknowledged this fact in a former publication [Sadeghi, Oberlack & Gauding, “On new scaling laws in a temporally evolving turbulent plane jet using Lie symmetry analysis and direct numerical simulation – Corrigendum”, J. Fluid Mech. **885**, E1 (2020)]. However, the Corrigendum is not cited and so the reader is not made aware that their method has fundamental problems that lead to inconsistencies and conflicting results. Instead, the very same nonphysical symmetry gets published again.

To validate their newly developed modeling ansatz, which essentially resulted into what they called ‘minimal’ turbulence model, Eqs.(73-76), Klingenberg *et al.*¹ give a proof-of-concept in Sec.IV.E. By choosing the flow configuration of an inviscid spatially evolving turbulent planar jet flow, they come to the conclusion that their model can generate scaling laws which go beyond the classical ones and therefore can describe effects which classical scaling laws aren’t capable of. But the authors did not examine their new scaling laws Eqs.(79-80) carefully enough. For example, consider the associated balance equations for the axial and transverse momentum of an inviscid spatially evolving planar turbulent jet flow in their statistically exact and *non-modeled* form^{2,3}

$$\bar{U}_j \frac{\partial \bar{U}_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial R_{ij}^{(0)}}{\partial x_j}, \quad \frac{\partial \bar{U}_i}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad i, j = 1, 2. \quad (1)$$

In contrast to the viscous case which exhibits two intrinsic global scales (see Ref. 4 and the references therein), the inviscid system (1) only offers a single one, the globally constant momentum flux⁵

$$J = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\bar{U}_1^2 + R_{11}^{(0)} + \bar{P} - P_{\infty} \right) dx_2. \quad (2)$$

Since one global scale is missing in this system, a global length (L) or time scale (T) cannot be constructed. Hence one is forced to reduce them to local scales, where, in order to be consistent with the scaling in Ref. 1, we take the axial coordinate as the length scale which defines the time scale then as⁴

$$L = x_1, \quad T = x_1^{3/2} / J^{1/2}. \quad (3)$$

Now, to search for self-similar regime(s) in a solution, we make the general ansatz of reducing the number of coordinates. In particular, we make the ansatz of a dimensionless self-similar variable:^{4,5}

$$(x_1, x_2) \rightarrow \tilde{x} = x_2/x_1, \quad (4)$$

which therefore, since \tilde{x} is dimensionless, leads to an ansatz of dimensionless field functions

$$\bar{U}_i(x_1, x_2) \rightarrow \tilde{U}_i(\tilde{x}), \quad R_{ij}^{(0)}(x_1, x_2) \rightarrow \tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}(\tilde{x}). \quad (5)$$

With the local velocity scale, $L/T = (J/x_1)^{1/2}$, they can be scaled into their dimensionally correct form⁶

$$\frac{\bar{U}_i(x_1, x_2)}{(J/x_1)^{1/2}} = \tilde{U}_i(\tilde{x}), \quad \frac{R_{ij}^{(0)}(x_1, x_2)}{J/x_1} = \tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}(\tilde{x}), \quad (6)$$

consistently reducing then the PDE-system (1) into an ODE-system with respect to the single variable \tilde{x} (4). Whether this ansatz is valid or not within a certain flow regime can only be decided by evaluating relations (6) through experimental or simulation data. If this is the case, then such a self-similarity is called a *self-similarity of the first kind*,⁷ since ansatz (6), with its self-similar variable (4), was established by dimensional analysis. In clear contrast to a solution if it shows a *self-similarity of the second kind* which cannot be established by dimensional analysis alone and therefore cannot be detected by the simple ansatz (6). Such self-similarities are characterized by additionally having to solve a nonlinear eigenvalue problem in order to determine the self-similar variable.⁷

Hence, for the inviscid case, result (6) is the only physically consistent ansatz to search for self-similar solutions in a spatially evolving planar turbulent jet flow, if, and this is important, if the self-similar variable is set to be of the form (4). Any other ansatz which makes use of the

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same self-similar variable (4), but which is not functionally equivalent to (6), will be inconsistent in one way or the other, as the one proposed by Eq.(80) in Ref. 1.

While Eq.(79) corresponds to the self-similar velocity result obtained in (6) and thus is correct, it is Eq.(80) for the Reynolds stresses which is flawed. Although Eq.(80)

$$R_{ij}^{(0)} = \tilde{H}_{ij}(\tilde{x})x_1^{-A_2} - \tilde{U}_i(\tilde{x})\tilde{U}_j(\tilde{x})x_1^{-1}, \quad \tilde{x} = x_2/x_1, \quad (7)$$

was obtained with the Lie-group symmetry method, which itself allows to investigate the similarity solutions of the first and second kind systematically, it results in a scale $x_1^{-A_2}$ which, for $A_2 \neq 1$, has no physical origin of the flow considered. Since the similarity solution (7) is defined with respect to the very same self-similar variable as (4), it therefore *cannot* be identified as a self-similarity of the second kind,⁴ simply because (4) is the result of a dimensional scaling and thus, by construction, associated to a similarity of the first kind — that (7) indeed constitutes a similarity of the *first kind* is also independently supported by the fact that (7) rests on three *global scaling* symmetries, as clearly expressed in the derivation of (7) through Eqs.(D3-D4) in Ref. 1. But, as just explained before, a physically consistent self-similar solution of the *first kind* with respect to the dimensionless self-similar variable $\tilde{x} = x_2/x_1$ (4), is and can only be given by (6)

$$R_{ij}^{(0)} = J \cdot \tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}(\tilde{x})x_1^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where the dimensionless function $\tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}$ can further be represented or decomposed into the *H*-framework of Ref. 1:

$$\tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}(\tilde{x}) = \tilde{H}_{ij}(\tilde{x}) - \tilde{U}_i(\tilde{x})\tilde{U}_j(\tilde{x}). \quad (9)$$

Hence, when comparing (8)-(9) with (7), we see that the latter solution can only be physically consistent if $A_2 = 1$. This clearly indicates that a scaling based on $A_2 \neq 1$ is nothing but a pure mathematical artefact, which is rooted in the fact that one of the three scalings in Ref. 1 to derive (7), namely Eq.(41), is not a true symmetry but only a superficial equivalence transformation resulting from the statistically unclosed equations (1), which, by closer inspection, even turns out to be a nonphysical equivalence transformation⁸ — for all details we refer to our full and unabridged Comment, Ref. 4. Therein we also give a further proof that the consistency of (7) can only be restored if $A_2 = 1$, which we independently demonstrate by considering the free-shear boundary-layer approximation of the governing system (1). Hence, in contrast as to what is claimed in Ref. 1, their newly proposed scaling laws Eqs.(79-80) do not go beyond any classical solutions, irrespective of whether we consider exact statistical balance equations or approximate ones.

A key aspect to be recognized in this whole discussion here is that since the statistical equations of turbulence are unclosed, so is their admitted set of invariant Lie-group transformations. Unclosed equations, as those considered in Ref. 1 to determine their new ‘symmetries’,

inevitably lead to infinite dimensional Lie-algebras, which means that (nearly) any invariant transformation can be generated, and thus also (nearly) any desirable scaling law. Ultimately one has an infinite set of invariant possibilities to choose from when performing a full and correct Lie-group symmetry analysis for unclosed equations.⁹⁻¹¹ A crucial information which is not shared with the reader in Ref. 1.

Hence, the Lie-group symmetry method in turbulence is *not* free of any assumptions. It is an ad-hoc method too, not in the same but in a similar way as the classical self-similarity method: Instead of using an *a priori* set of scales, the Lie-group method has to make use of an *a priori* set of symmetries, namely to select the correct relevant symmetries from an infinite (unclosed) set. In other words, the particular selection of the additionally chosen symmetries Eqs.(41-44) in Ref. 1 is an assumption and *not* a result that comes from theory, as the authors try to convey. Because, as just referenced before, when correctly performing a complete and systematic Lie-group symmetry analysis on the considered set of unclosed equations (1), including its infinite hierarchy of all unclosed higher order correlation equations as presented in their study Ref. 12, one gets an infinite set of functionally independent invariances, and not only those few reported in Ref. 12 and presented here again through Eqs.(34-44) in Ref. 1 — to note is that all ‘new’ invariances in Ref. 12, or equally in Ref. 13, were obtained only through heuristics and a trial-and-error ansatz, and *not* through a complete and systematic Lie-group analysis, which would have given an unclosed set of invariances and thus an overall different conclusion, namely that the Lie-group method alone, like any other analytical method, cannot bypass the closure problem of turbulence.

Another concerning issue not mentioned in Ref. 1 is the fact that due to the arbitrariness involved when making a particular choice from an infinite (unclosed) set of possible symmetries, there is a high chance that one will select a nonphysical symmetry which is not reflected by experiment or numerical simulation. This clearly is the case in Ref. 1, not only for the chosen scaling symmetry Eq.(41), but also for the arbitrarily chosen set of translation symmetries Eqs.(42-44). Although knowing better that this set of symmetries is nonphysical and not supported by experiment or simulation, as clearly acknowledged by one of the authors (M. Oberlack) in Ref. 14, it nevertheless gets published and used again in their current study Ref. 1 to model turbulent flows.^{15,16}

But using the result of Ref. 14 and explicitly excluding the jet-flow configuration from their analysis and thus from their newly proposed generic model Eqs.(73-76) in Ref. 1, would have required an explicit explanation by the authors to counter the question: *Why to exclude from a generic turbulence model such a basic canonical flow as jet flow?* It’s clear that exclusion of such a basic flow configuration will give the impression that something is fundamentally wrong with this model, and indeed it is!

The modeling strategy by Klingenberg *et al.*¹ is methodologically flawed on three counts:^{4,17}

(i) Their key modeling-argument in itself is circular: *Two new ‘symmetries’, Eq.(41) & Eqs.(42-44), are extracted from unclosed equations to then use them in order to find improved closing constraints for those same (!) equations again.* This effort is comparable to pull oneself up by one’s own bootstraps.

(ii) Although the authors recognize already early on that there is a natural barrier Eq.(68) that prevents them from implementing these two symmetries, they nevertheless force this implementation by artificially pushing up the number of variables, which, obviously, is not a very advantageous and promising procedure as a modeler.¹⁸ As a peculiar result they obtain the full (inviscid) Navier-Stokes equations as the modeled equations again, Eqs.(73-74), which means that their modeling strategy is even based on a further, second circular argument: *Equations get modeled by equations which are exactly the same (!) as those being modeled.*

(iii) Their new modeling variables (\tilde{U}_i, \tilde{P}), being different to the mean fields (\bar{U}_i, \bar{P}), cannot be given a physical meaning although they each carry a simple physical dimension, that of velocity and pressure, respectively. Their explanation in Sec.IV.D to give those fields at least some meaning fails.⁴ In fact, as explained and discussed in Ref. 17, these new fields are all physically fictitious and do not exist.

To close this comment, it should not go unmentioned that Klingenberg *et al.*¹ makes numerous false and unfounded statements in addition to those already mentioned herein. They are all listed in our unabridged Comment, Ref. 4, which in each case also explains why a correction is necessary.

Nota bene: From the present Comment it should be clear that we do not criticize the method of Lie-groups itself, which is a very useful mathematical tool indeed, when only applied to the right problems.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study.

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- ⁵ D. Coles, *Topics in Shear Flow: The Plane Jet* (Caltech, 2017).
- ⁶ It goes without saying that the dimensionless functions $\tilde{U}_i, \tilde{R}_{ij}^{(0)}$ are still analytical unknowns of the system. Note, the self-similar solution ansatz for pressure follows that of the Reynolds stresses.
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- ⁸ More precisely, Eq.(41) is a physically *non-realizable* equivalence transformation, meaning that although Eq.(41) leaves the

- originally unclosed statistical equations invariant, the transformed statistical fields cannot be physically realized.^{11,19–23} In other words, according to the transformation rule of Eq.(41), if the non-transformed fields $\bar{U}_i, \bar{P}, H_{ij}$, etc., define a statistical solution set of the deterministic Navier-Stokes equations, then the transformed set of statistical fields $\bar{U}_i^*, \bar{P}^*, H_{ij}^*$, etc., do *not* form statistical solutions anymore, which can emerge or which can be generated from the deterministic and thus closed Navier-Stokes equations. They are thus not realizable and therefore, ultimately, nonphysical.
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 - ¹⁵ Important to note here is that the statistical translation symmetry Eqs.(42-44) in Ref. 1 is exactly the same symmetry as in Refs. 14 & 24, and not any variant thereof. For details, see Ref. 4.
 - ¹⁶ What’s additionally disturbing here is that instead of citing the JFM-Corrigendum (Ref. 14), the flawed original paper Ref. 24 gets cited as Ref.(33), however not self-critical, but in the straight opposite way, presented as a paper that has no faults at all. In particular it is praised as an overall successful paper, not only once but several times after the nonphysical translation symmetry Eqs.(42-44) was introduced on p.6.
 - ¹⁷ M. Frewer, “Review of ‘Symmetry-based turbulence modeling’,” [publon:27659704](https://publons.com/publon/27659704) (2019).
 - ¹⁸ As a modeler one usually prefers to use Occam’s razor as a basis, in that unnecessarily complex models should not be preferred to simpler ones. In fact, this blind focus on symmetries, especially in turbulence modeling as exercised in Ref. 1, limits creativity considerably. Freely adapted from Mies van der Rohe, it’s here valid to say: *“Symmetry is the tool of the unimaginative”* — In this context it is worth reading Ref. 25, to realize that the arguments presented therein may also apply to turbulence modeling.
 - ¹⁹ M. Frewer, G. Khujadze, and H. Foysi, “On the physical inconsistency of a new statistical scaling symmetry in incompressible Navier-Stokes turbulence.” [arXiv:1412.3061](https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.3061) (2014).
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